

Comparative Evaluation of Propofol-Ketamine, Propofol Fentanyl and Propofol-Dexmedetomidine in Terms of Hemodynamic Variables and Recovery Characteristics in Upper Abdominal Surgeries under General Anaesthesia

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Abstract:

Introduction: Balanced General Anesthesia is a state that encompasses multiple components like amnesia, analgesia, hypnosis, muscle relaxation and reduced reflex responses. To achieve this balanced state, anesthesiologists carefully combine different combination of drugs.

Aim and Objectives: Primary objective of present study comparative evaluation of propofol – ketamine, propofol – fentanyl and propofol – dexmedetomidine in terms of hemodynamic variables and recovery characteristics in upper abdominal studies under general anaesthesia. Secondary objective is to evaluate and compare the hemodynamic variables and associated side effects after administering the combination of above mentioned drugs.

Materials & Methods: After approval of Institutional Ethical Committee, a prospective comparative study was conducted on 114 patients belonging to ASA Physical Status I & II patients in an age group of 18-60years, undergoing elective upper-abdominal surgeries under general anaesthesia after taking informed consent. Patients were grouped into 3 groups of 38 each depending upon the drug combinations used. Propofol 2mg/kg of induction dose followed by 2mg/kg/hr of maintenance dose along with ketamine 2mg/kg for induction & 1mg/kg/hr for maintenance in Group A, fentanyl 2mcg/kg for induction & 1mcg/kg maintenance dose in Group B, dexmedetomidine 2mcg/kg of induction dose & 1mcg/kg/hr for maintenance in Group C. Heart rate, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, sedation score assessed at specified time intervals. Post-operative recovery, post-operative complications, pain, analgesic requirement were recorded. Hemodynamic parameters were compared using ANOVA.

Results: Demographic characteristics were comparable between all three groups. Significant decrease in heart rate, blood pressure with propofol-dexmedetomidine ($p < 0.05$) compared to propofol-ketamine, propofol-fentanyl observed. Early recovery observed with group B followed by group A and C. Better sedation noted in group C followed by group A and B. Patients in propofol-fentanyl, propofol-dexmedetomidine group had early onset pain, and need for analgesia was more compared to propofol-ketamine group.

Conclusion: Propofol-dexmedetomidine, propofol-ketamine combination is extensively effective in maintaining hemodynamic stability, with faster recovery observed with propofol-fentanyl compared to other combinations. Propofol-dexmedetomidine, propofol-ketamine combination comparatively provided better analgesia peri-operatively.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine; Fentanyl; GA; Hemodynamic parameters; Ketamine.

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Introduction

General anesthesia should ideally offer a swift and Comfortable onset, reliable and transition to unconsciousness, stable and controlled vital signs during the procedure, minimal side effects and complications and rapid and smooth return to

consciousness, with prompt recovery of vital reflexes and cognitive functions. [1] Balanced General Anesthesia is a state that encompasses multiple components like amnesia, analgesia, hypnosis, muscle relaxation and reduced reflex

responses. To achieve this balanced state, anesthesiologists carefully combine different combination of drugs. [2] The use of barbiturates, benzodiazepines, and Propofol at the dosages required reducing reaction to laryngoscopy and intubation is linked to significant hemodynamic side effects. [1] It is crucial to keep in mind that, in order to reduce hemodynamic stimulation, the laryngoscopy and intubation times should align with the agents maximal effects. Adjuvants such as opioids are commonly utilized and seem to have a graded effect on blunting hemodynamic responses.[1] Propofol is extremely lipophilic and rapidly penetrates the blood-brain barrier, allowing for an early onset of action and speedy recovery. It has no analgesic effect. Propofol's primary drawback is its potential to create sudden deep drowsiness, which increases the risk of respiratory and cardiovascular depression. [3]

When ketamine and Propofol (Ketofol) are used together, less medicine is needed to create a stable structure. Although it works quickly, healing may take longer. [4] The persistence of normal or very slightly reduced laryngeal and pharyngeal reflexes is linked to unconsciousness. After a ketamine injection induction dose, return of awareness often happens in 10 to 20 minutes, but full orientation, recovery could take an extra 60 to 90 minutes. [5]

Dexmedetomidine has analgesic efficacy in addition to sedative effects. Although mild respiratory depression has several benefits, it can also result in bradycardia and hypotension. It should be used cautiously because it interacts synergistically with opioids and other sedatives.

For mild to severe sedation, dexmedetomidine is used. For deeper sedation, it could be preferable to add Propofol. [2] When dexmedetomidine dosages are large, complete IV anesthesia is produced without concomitant respiratory depression.

To achieve the balanced state under general anesthesia, present study was planned by carefully combining different combination of drugs.

Aim and objectives:

Primary objective of present study comparative evaluation of propofol – ketamine, propofol – fentanyl and propofol – dexmedetomidine in terms of hemodynamic variables and recovery characteristics in upper abdominal studies under general anaesthesia. Secondary objective is to evaluate and compare the hemodynamic variables and associated side effects after administering the combination of above mentioned drugs.

Materials & Methods:

The study was done as a cross-sectional study at the Department of Anaesthesiology, Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Research Centre, located in Tumkur, Karnataka, India. Patients aged 18-60 years, classified as ASA Class I & II, who were undergoing elective upper abdominal surgery under general anesthesia, were recruited for the research after obtaining clearance from the institutional ethics committee (Ref No.: SSMC/MED/IEC-133/July-2022) and informed consent from the patients.

Patients with pre-diagnosed systemic illness, expected difficult airway, pregnant or lactational mothers, having BMI >29.9 kg/m², or unwilling to give consent were excluded from the study.

Sample size calculation was done by employing Purposive sampling technique & the formula for calculating the sample size was $n = 2[Z(1-\alpha/2) + Z(1-\beta)]^2 \times \sigma^2 / d^2$. The minimum sample size required was 34 in each group (total – 102). Considering the non-response rate of 10%, the total sample size required was 38 in each group (total = 114).

All the selected 114 patients were allocated into one of the three groups after pre-anaesthetic evaluation and routine work-up.

- **Group A:** receiving inj. Propofol 2.0 mg/kg and inj. Ketamine 2.0 mg/kg IV bolus doses for induction, followed by Infusion of Propofol 2.0mg/kg/h and Ketamine1.0mg/kg/h as maintenance dose
- **Group B:** receiving inj. Propofol 2.0 mg/kg and inj. Fentanyl 2.0 µg/kg IV bolus doses for induction, followed by Infusion of Propofol 2.0mg/kg/h and Fentanyl1.0µg/kg/h as maintenance dose
- **Group C:** receiving inj. Propofol 2.0 mg/kg and inj. Dexmedetomidine 1.0 µg/kg IV bolus doses for induction, followed by Infusion of Propofol 2.0mg/kg/h and Dexmedetomidine 1.0 µg/kg/h as maintenance dose

All the hemodynamic variables (Heart rate, SBP, DBP, MAP, Respiratory rate, EtCO₂, SpO₂) were observed before, during and after induction at intervals of every minute up to 5 mins, every 5 mins up to 60 mins and every 10 mins till the end of the procedure. Depth of sedation was also observed by using Modified Ramsay sedation scale during the procedure. All the infusions were stopped 5-7 minutes before the anticipated end of surgery. After extubation, the recovery characteristics of the patients were assessed using Aldrete's recovery score at immediate post-extubation period and 10 mins after that.

Parameter scores

Saturation: SpO ₂ >90% on room air	2
SpO ₂ >90% on oxygen	1
SpO ₂ <90% on oxygen	0
Respiration: Breathes deeply and coughs freely	2
Dyspnoeic, shallow or limited breathing	1
Apnoea	0
Circulation: Blood pressure +20mm Hg of normal	2
Blood pressure +20 – 50mmHg of normal	1
Blood pressure more than +50mm Hg of normal	0
Consciousness: Fully awake	2
Arousable on calling	1
Not responsive	0
Activity: Moves all extremities	2
Moves two extremities	1
Unable to move extremities	0

Recovery characteristics, post-operative complications and the need for rescue analgesia were observed among the three groups.

Statistical Analysis:

The data was entered in excel spread sheet. For quantitative data, descriptive statistical analysis was performed using the mean and standard deviation; for categorical variables, frequency and percentages were used. Using the chi-square test, the relationship between category variables was

examined. Repeated measure analysis was used to examine the treatment effect between groups. To check for differences in the parameters at various time intervals, an ANOVA will be used. The analysis was conducted using SPSS version-20 statistical software.

Results:

The demographic characteristics among the groups were found to be similar and comparable ($p>0.05$). [Table 1]

Table 1: Demographic data

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P- Value	
Age (years) (Mean±SD)	36.55±8.494	40.96±10.309	35.24±13.435	0.42 (NS)	
Gender	Male	22 (31.9%)	20 (29.0%)	27 (39.1%)	0.80 (NS)
	Female	16 (35.6%)	18 (40.0%)	11 (24.4%)	
Weight (kg) (Mean±SD)	53.00±8.161	60.14±10.061	54.71±10.099	0.12 (NS)	
ASA grade	I	32 (33.3%)	34 (35.4%)	30 (31.3%)	0.43 (NS)
	II	06 (33.3%)	04 (22.2%)	08 (44.4%)	
Duration of surgery (minutes)	63.16±18.760	68.49±18.566	62.63±17.658	0.52 (NS)	

NS- Non Significant

There was a significant intra-group ($p<0.001$) and inter-group ($p<0.001$) differences in heart rate during the period of study. Variations in heart rate were statistically significant between group C with group A ($p<0.001$) and group B ($p<0.001$) when compared to group A with group B ($p=0.990$) during the observation period.

There was significant difference in the Systolic Blood pressure in all groups during the period of study ($p<0.001$) with significant inter group differences ($p<0.001$). The difference seen between the groups A and C ($p<0.001$) and B and C ($p<0.001$) was statistically significant than between group A and B ($p=0.461$) during the observation period.

There was significant difference in the Diastolic Blood pressure in all groups during the period of

study ($p<0.001$) with significant inter group differences ($p<0.001$). The difference seen between the groups A and C ($p<0.001$) and B and C ($p<0.001$) was statistically significant than that between group A and B ($p=0.179$) during the observation period.

There was statistically significant differences in Mean Arterial blood Pressure (MAP) among intra-group ($p<0.001$) and inter-group ($p<0.001$) as observed during the study period. The difference noted between groups A, group C ($p<0.001$) and group B, group C ($p<0.001$) was statistically significant than that between groups A and B ($p=0.213$) during the observation period.

There was no significant intra-group ($p>0.05$) and inter-group ($p>0.05$) differences seen in oxygen saturation (SpO₂) and End-tidal Carbon dioxide

(EtCO₂) between groups A, B and C during the observation period. [Table 2]

Table 2: Inter group variations – Hemodynamic parameters

Intergroup difference	P- value		
	Group A vs. Group B	Group A vs. Group C	Group B vs. Group C
Heart rate (HR)	0.990 (NS)	<0.001 (S)	<0.001 (S)
Systolic Blood pressure (SBP)	0.461 (NS)	<0.001 (S)	<0.001 (S)
Diastolic Blood pressure (DBP)	0.179 (NS)	<0.001 (S)	<0.001 (S)
Mean Arterial pressure (MAP)	0.213 (NS)	<0.001 (S)	<0.001 (S)
Oxygen Saturation (SpO ₂)	0.221 (NS)	0.640 (NS)	0.064 (NS)
End-tidal Carbon dioxide (EtCO ₂)	0.685 (NS)	0.946 (NS)	0.636 (NS)

NS- Non Significant, S- Significant

Figure 1: Hear Rate

Figure 2: Systolic Blood Pressure

Figure 3: Diastolic Blood Pressure

Figure 4: Mean Arterial blood Pressure

Figure 5: Oxygen Saturation

Figure 6: End tidal Carbon-dioxide(EtCO₂)

Statistically significant differences were seen in Modified Ramsay Sedation score during the observation period among intra-group ($p < 0.05$) and inter-group ($p < 0.05$) as observed during the study period. The difference noted between groups A, group C ($p = 0.02$) and group B, group C ($p = 0.012$) was statistically significant than that between groups A and B ($p = 0.2$) during the observation period. [Table 3]

Table 3: Inter group variations Modified Ramsay Sedation score

Intergroup difference in Modified Ramsay Sedation score		P- value
Group A	Group B	0.200 (NS)
Group A	Group C	0.022 (S)
Group B	Group C	0.012 (S)

NS- Non Significant, S- Significant

The post-operative complications were seen in all the three groups, whereas group B showed relatively more postoperative complications compared to group A and comparatively less side effects in group C. However, there was no significant statistical difference in the post-operative complications with $p > 0.05$. Pain after the

surgery as assessed by Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) showed no significant difference with p value of 0.4 (p value > 0.05).

All three groups of drug combinations are effective in providing intraoperative analgesia. [Table 4]

Table 4: Chi square test for different parameters

Parameters	Pearson Chi square test	
	Value	P-value
Modified Aldrete's Recovery Score at different time interval	Immediately post-extubation	15.9
	10 minutes post-extubation	14.6
Post-operative complication		18.1
VAS score		3.6

NS- Non Significant, S- Significant

There is significance difference in between the groups ($p < 0.001$) in terms of time duration, postoperatively when the patient required rescue analgesia. Group B required rescue analgesia earlier compared to group A and then compared to group C. [Table 5]

Table 5: Mean duration of rescue analgesia

Groups	Mean (mins)	Standard deviation	ANOVA test	
			F value	P-value
A	26.05	11.692	9.3	< 0.0001 (NS)
B	32.11	8.748		
C	21.32	11.951		

NS- Non Significant

Discussion

In order to provide balanced general anaesthesia for upper abdominal surgeries, ensuring patient safety,

comfort and optimal surgical conditions is vital. Strategic combination of drugs and techniques to address the diverse needs of anaesthesia,

minimizing side effects and promoting rapid recovery was implemented in this study.

Each of the three groups in this study—propofol-ketamine, propofol-fentanyl, and propofol-dexmedetomidine—shared similar demographic characteristics. Studies by Nanjiah Y et al. [6], Bajwa et al. [7], Pandey, S et al. [8] and Ramdev, B et al. [9] all came to similar conclusions. This disproves the notion that confounding variables might account for observed dose disparities. As far as the hemodynamic parameters are concerned, there was a slight decrease in heart rate (9%) in propofol-fentanyl group as compared to propofol-ketamine combination in the study of Mayer et al. [10] and Mi et al. [11]

Sangeeta Chauhan et al studied that there was a fall in pulse rate in propofol-ketamine group attributing to myocardial depressant action of propofol. But the fall in Propofol-Fentanyl group was significant ($p > 0.05$) at 1, 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 min after induction this difference may be due to sympathomimetic activity of ketamine which acts to counteract the myocardial depressant action of propofol. [12] The dexmedetomidine-propofol group showed higher intra-procedural hemodynamic stability than the ketamine-propofol group, according to study by Mohamed Sidky and colleagues. Even though substantial intra-procedural statistical differences were noted; the dexmedetomidine-propofol group's HR values were lower. [13]

Anushakarkala et al [14], in a study of intravenous Dexmedetomidine-Ketamine (DK) Versus Ketamine-Propofol (KP) for Procedural Sedation in Adults Undergoing Short Surgical Procedures our study, subjects in Group DK maintained lower heart rate when compared to Group KP, but statistical significance was appreciated only at 12 minutes post-induction. Dexmedetomidine decreases heart rate by decreasing norepinephrine levels. A decrease in heart rate with dexmedetomidine was observed in other studies such as Tosun Z et al [15] and Joshi VS et al [16]

Ghomeishi A et al [17] concluded that the heart rate level had a statistically significant difference in all stages of measurement after induction in the two groups with propofol and dexmedetomidine, which showed increasing and decreasing trends respectively.

The increasing trend in propofol only group attributable to the increased response to surgical stress. In a non-major type of surgery study by Chattopadhyay et al. [18], dexmedetomidine group had lower heart rate in comparison to propofol, which was consistent with the results of the present study. Dexmedetomidine usage is associated with a greater decrease in heart rate, in part because of its sympatholytic effects, but also because of a vagal

mimetic effect. The most significant cardiovascular effect of propofol during the induction of anaesthesia is a drop in the blood pressure, seen in all groups of patients. In their study, Srivastava VK et al., administered induction dose of propofol guided by BIS after same loading dose of dexmedetomidine and determined significant decreases in blood pressure levels compared to preoperative value [19]. In a study by Azemati et al. [20], after induction, the mean heart rate significantly decreased in both propofol groups compared to baseline, and remained below baseline until the end of the surgery.

Patients who received propofol and ketamine had stable hemodynamics, while those who received midazolam-ketamine had a considerably higher number of hypertensive peaks, according to a study by Hernandez et al. [21].

Studies were conducted by Abbas et al. [22] using propofol alone, ketamine+propofol, and dexmedetomidine+propofol. They tracked changes in heart rate and mean arterial pressure as part of their evaluation. In the group that received propofol alone, heart rate decreased significantly, whereas in the group that received propofol and ketamine, mean arterial pressure increased significantly. Our results are consistent with those of the dexmedetomidine group, who reported more stable hemodynamics.

Mohamed Sidky et al, studied that statistically significant differences existed amongst the two groups (propofol-ketamine) and (propofol-dexmedetomidine) regarding intra-procedural MAP fluctuations, with the exception of the record assessed at 20 min. The dexmedetomidine-propofol group had lower MAP values, similar to our study. [23]

According to Mahajan et al. [24], comparison of ketamine and fentanyl, added to propofol in TIVA, both groups saw a statistically insignificant small rise. Hypotension was revealed in 5 patients received fentanyl-propofol while none in ketamine propofol groups; this evidence was in accordance with our study.

Nazemroaya, et al. [25] observed that arterial SpO₂ were not significantly different between the propofol-ketamine and propofol-fentanyl groups as well as in each of the two groups before, during and after the procedure ($p > 0.05$). They also concluded that the mean pain intensity was significantly lower in the propofol-fentanyl group than the propofol-ketamine group [25].

Tekeli et al., [26] concluded in their study that ketamine-propofol combination was superior in terms of early recovery compared to dexmedetomidine-propofol combination, which was similar to our study.

Conclusion

Propofol-Dexmedetomidine and Propofol-Ketamine combination are more effective than Propofol-fentanyl for maintaining the hemodynamic stability during upper abdominal surgeries under General Anaesthesia. Propofol-ketamine produces better hemodynamic stability during anaesthesia; it is a better choice especially when hemodynamic stability is great importance. Propofol-Fentanyl group showed faster recovery from Anaesthesia when compared with Propofol-Ketamine and Propofol-Dexmedetomidine group. However, Propofol-Ketamine and Propofol-Dexmedetomidine provided better analgesia perioperatively and the duration of need for rescue analgesia was prolonged in these two groups compared to Propofol-Fentanyl group. Dexmedetomidine is most appropriate adjuvant because it reduces the pain level and the amount of Propofol to be administered to the greatest extent and is not different from other agents in terms of satisfaction score and side effects.

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